

Impact of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) Practices on Norbuling Rigter College (NRC) Staff Job Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT: Employee job satisfaction is a key factor for the organization's growth and development. Satisfied employees are preferred because they make the working environment conducive. Employee job satisfaction and resource efficiency are linked to green HRM practices. Employees may be more satisfied if the organization adopted green practices. This study aims to the impact of different dimensions of Green Human Resource management practices on the job satisfaction of Norbuling Rigter College (NRC) staff. For this purpose the Quantitative research with a descriptive approach was used. The survey data were collected using Google form from 46 staff of Norbuling Rigter College (NRC), Paro. The questionnaire is adapted from the study of Nath and Goel (2018). Certain modifications are made to the questionnaire to suit the requirements of the study. All questions are Likert scale questions. The study recommends that the NRC should prioritize sustainable practices in their recruitment and training process to ensure that new employees are aware of and committed to the organization's sustainability goals and should encourage employee participation in green initiatives through communication and incentives to increase engagement.

Introduction:

GHRM practices involve various policies and strategies aimed at reducing environmental impacts in organizations. These practices include but are not limited to energy and resource conservation, waste reduction, and recycling, green procurement, eco-friendly transportation, and the adoption of sustainable practices in product design and production. The adoption of GHRM practices also involves the promotion of environmental awareness among employees and the development of a culture of sustainability within the organization.

GHRM practices also influence employee job satisfaction through other factors, such as employee engagement, motivation, and commitment. For instance, the adoption of GHRM practices can improve employee engagement by providing them with opportunities to participate in environmental initiatives and

promoting a sense of purpose beyond profit. Similarly, GHRM practices can improve employee motivation and commitment by demonstrating the organization's commitment to social and environmental responsibility.

The linkages between GHRM practices and employee job satisfaction in the organization are becoming increasingly evident in recent research. Organizations that adopt GHRM practices are likely to experience improved employee job satisfaction, engagement, motivation, and commitment. These linkages are crucial in enhancing organizational performance and competitiveness in the current business environment. Future research should explore these linkages further and provide insights into the mechanisms underlying these linkages.

Measures of job satisfaction look at how content workers are in general and how they feel about particular aspects of their occupations, such as the tasks they do and the degree to which they are supervised. The success of an organization relies heavily on the happiness of its workers. Satisfied employees are preferred because they make the working environment conducive. Employee job satisfaction and resource efficiency are linked to green HRM practices. Employees may be more satisfied if the organization adopted green practices. Green HRM practices will also have an impact on how office resources are used, resulting in resource efficiency.

Review of Literature:

Ahmad and Umrani (2019) conducted a study to understand the impact of ethical leadership style on job satisfaction with the mediating role of GHRM practices. The researchers collected data from 177 respondents from Pakistan public sector organizations. The findings revealed that GHRM practices have an impact on employee job satisfaction. The employees perceive that green recruitment and green training is a form of support provided by the employer, which makes employees' professional experience more satisfying. Therefore, it is important to guarantee the right application of HRM with productive consequences, and this is something that may be achieved via green HRM.

Franklin and Nilufar (2018) conducted a study with scheduled banks to examine whether GHRM practices influence employees' job satisfaction or not. The sample size used for the purpose of the study is 172. The findings revealed that GHRM has a positive influence on employee job satisfaction. In addition, the study results showed that the majority of respondents understand the concept of GHRM. Green practices within the organization have the potential to make employees satisfied.

Statement of the Problem: By reviewing the different literature on the concept of GHRM practices and their influence on employees' job satisfaction it is inferred that GHRM is a vital component of the organization's growth and development. The organization that has adopted the GHRM practices is successful in terms of the growth and retention of its employees. Therefore the problem stated here is “Impact of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) Practices on Norbuling Rigter College (NRC) Staff Job Satisfaction”

Objectives: The present study has been carried out with the following objectives-

- To study the impact of different dimensions of Green Human Resource management practices on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.

Hypothesis:

HO1-Green recruitment and training have a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.

HO2-The green reward system has a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.

HO3-Green employee involvement has a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.

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Methodology:

Research Design

The study employed Quantitative research with a descriptive approach.

Number of Respondents Participated in the Study

The survey data were collected from 46 respondents.

Study Area

Norbuling Rigter College, Paro, Bhutan

Data Collection Procedure: The survey data were collected using Google form .

Development of Questionnaire: The questionnaire is adapted from the study of Nath and Goel (2018). Certain modifications are made to the questionnaire to suit the requirements of the study. All questions are Likert scale questions.

Questionnaire Reliability and Validity: As the survey instrument was adapted from previous studies, content validity was already established. For reliability, checking Cronbach's alpha was calculated. The Cronbach's alpha score was at 0.874 for the 25 items that is considered as quite good and acceptable.

Data Analysis Technique: The data were analyzed with the help of excel software. Regression, Correlation, are prepared for examining the research objectives.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Description

Table 1: Gender * Teaching or Non-Teaching Cross Tabulation

			Teaching or Non-Teaching		Total
			Teaching	Non-Teaching	
Gender	M	Count	12	6	18
		% of Total	26.1%	13.0%	39.1%
	F	Count	14	14	28
		% of Total	30.4%	30.4%	60.9%
Total		Count	26	20	46
		% of Total	56.5%	43.5%	100.0%

The table 1 shows a cross tabulation of gender (male and female) and whether the person is in a teaching or non-teaching profession. There are a total of 46 individuals in the sample. Out of those, 26 (56.5%) are in the teaching profession, and 20 (43.5%) are in the non-teaching profession. Among male individuals, there are 12 in the teaching profession and 6 in the non-teaching profession. This means that 26.1% of the total samples are males, and 13.0% of the total sample are males in non-teaching professions. Among female individuals, there are 14 in the teaching profession and 14 in the non-teaching profession. This means that 30.4% of the total sample are females in teaching professions, and 30.4% of the total sample are females in non-teaching professions.

Table 2: Age * Teaching or Non-Teaching Cross Tabulation

			Teaching or Non-Teaching		Total	
			Teaching	Non-Teaching		
Age	20-30 Years	Count	14	14	28	
		% of Total	30.4%	30.4%	60.9%	
	30-40 Years	Count	6	0	6	
		% of Total	13.0%	0.0%	13.0%	
	40-50 Years	Count	6	2	8	
		% of Total	13.0%	4.3%	17.4%	
	51-60 Years	Count	0	2	2	
		% of Total	0.0%	4.3%	4.3%	
	61 and above	Count	0	2	2	
		% of Total	0.0%	4.3%	4.3%	
	Total		Count	26	20	46
			% of Total	56.5%	43.5%	100.0%

The table 2 shows a cross tabulation of age categories (20-30, 30-40, 40-50, 51-60, 61 and above) and whether the person is in a teaching or non-teaching profession. There are a total of 46 individuals in the sample. Out of those, 26 (56.5%) are in the teaching profession, and 20 (43.5%) are in the non-teaching profession. In the 20-30 age category, there are 14 individuals in both the teaching and non-teaching professions, making it the most populated age group with 28 individuals (60.9% of the total sample). In the 30-40 age category, there are 6 individuals in the teaching profession and none in the non-teaching profession. In the 40-50 age category, there are 6 individuals in the teaching profession and 2 individuals in the non-teaching profession. In the 51-60 age category, there are no individuals in the teaching profession and 2 individuals in the non-teaching profession. In the 61 and above age category, there are no individuals in the teaching profession and 2 individuals in the non-teaching profession.

Table 3:Coefficients

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.719	.542		3.173	.003
	Green Recruitment and Training	.103	.156	.128	.659	.513
	Participation in Green Agenda	-.179	.221	-.125	-.808	.424
	Green Reward System	.554	.184	.608	3.012	.004

Job Satisfaction was the dependent variable, while the independent factors were Green Recruitment and Training, Participation in Green Agenda, and Green Reward System (see table 3 for the resulting coefficients). When controlling for all other factors, the "B" column displays the unstandardized regression coefficients, which indicate the percentage change in the dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) associated with a one-unit change in each independent variable. The variability in the estimated regression coefficient is shown as a standard error in the "Std. Error" column. Standardized regression coefficients (shown in the "Beta" column) indicate the amount by which the dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) would vary if each

independent variable were to change by one standard deviation, while all other variables were held constant. Each regression coefficient's t-value, indicating whether or not it is statistically distinct from zero, is shown in the "t" column. For each regression coefficient, the "Sig." column displays the significance level, which is the likelihood of finding a t-value as severe as the one recorded under the null hypothesis that the regression coefficient is zero. The findings reveal that the constant term, which reflects the expected value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero, is 1.719 (with a standard error of .542). Independent variable coefficients for Green Recruitment and Training and Participation in the Green Agenda are not substantially different from zero (p-values >.05), indicating that they do not predict Job Satisfaction.

However, the p-value for the Green Reward System coefficient is only .004, demonstrating that this variable is a robust predictor of Job Satisfaction. To be more precise, controlling for other factors, an increase of one unit in Green Reward System is connected with a 0.554 rise in Job Satisfaction.

The standardized coefficient (Beta) for Green Reward System is .608, which indicates that Green Reward System has a relatively strong effect on Job Satisfaction compared to the other independent variables in the model. The final regression equation is

$$Y = 1.719 + .608 X$$

Where, Y= Job Satisfaction and X= Green reward system

Table 4: Hypotheses Result

Hypotheses	P Value	S/NS
Green recruitment and training have a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.	0.513	Not Significant
The green reward system has a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.	0.004	Significant
Green employee involvement has a positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff.	0.424	Not Significant

According to the table 2, the green reward system has a significant positive influence on the job satisfaction of NRC staff, with a p-value of 0.004. This suggests that the effect of the green reward system on job satisfaction is unlikely to be due to chance, and the relationship is likely to be a real one.

In contrast, the other two hypotheses, green recruitment and training and green employee involvement, did not show statistically significant effects on job satisfaction, with p-values of 0.513 and 0.424, respectively. This means that there is not enough evidence to support the claim that these two green HR practices have a positive impact on job satisfaction.

In summary, the study found that the green reward system is a significant predictor of job satisfaction among NRC staff, while green recruitment and training and green employee involvement did not show significant effects. However, it's important to note that statistical significance does not necessarily mean practical or meaningful significance in real-world situations.

Recommendations

1. The NRC should prioritize sustainable practices in their recruitment and training process to ensure that new employees are aware of and committed to the organization's sustainability goals.
2. The NRC should focus on designing green jobs to increase the number of environmentally friendly roles within the organization.

3. The NRC should encourage employee participation in green initiatives through communication and incentives to increase engagement.
4. The NRC should consider implementing a Green Reward System to incentivize employees to engage in environmentally sustainable practices.
5. The NRC should ensure that their waste management practices are up to standard, as this is an area in which they have demonstrated moderate implementation.
6. The NRC should continue to prioritize designing an energy-efficient workspace to reduce their environmental footprint.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the analysis suggests that the NRC should continue to implement sustainable practices in the workplace, with a particular focus on designing green jobs and encouraging employee participation in green initiatives. Additionally, the NRC should consider incorporating sustainable practices into their recruitment and training process and implementing a green reward system to improve employee job satisfaction. By doing so, the NRC can enhance their sustainability efforts while also potentially improving employee well-being and retention rates.

References:

1. Al Battat, A. R., & Mat Som, A. P. (2014). Emergency planning and disaster recovery in Malaysian hospitality industry. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 144, 45-53.
2. Applebaum, D., Fowler, S., Fiedler, N., Osinubi, O., & Robson, M. (2010). The impact of environmental factors on nursing stress, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. *The Journal of nursing administration*, 40, 323.
3. Bibi, P., Ahmad, A., & Majid, A. H. (2018). HRM practices and employee retention: The moderating effect of work environment. In *Applying partial least squares in tourism and hospitality research*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
4. Bibi, P., Pangil, F., Johari, J., & Ahmad, A. (2017). The impact of compensation and promotional opportunities on employee retention in academic institutions: The moderating role of work environment. *Journal of Economic & Management Perspectives*, 11(1), 378-391.
5. Dodman, D. (2009), “Blaming cities for climate change? An analysis of urban greenhouse gas emissions inventories”, *Environment and Urbanization*, 21(1), 185-201.
6. Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human resource management*, 56(4), 613-627.
7. Gunaseelan, R., & Ollukkaran, B. A. (2012). A study on the impact of work environment on employee performance. *Namex International Journal of Management Research*, 71, 1-16.
8. Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis* (7th ed.). Englewood Cliffs: PrenticeHall.
9. Han, J. W., Kok, S. K., & McClelland, R. (2020). Impact of green training on employee turnover and customer satisfaction. In *17th International Conference on Intellectual Capital, Knowledge Management & Organisational Learning ICICKM 2020* (p. 423).
10. Jaworski, B. J. (1988). Toward a theory of marketing control: environmental context, control types, and consequences. *Journal of marketing*, 52(3), 23-39.

11. Kim-Soon, N., Ahmad, N., & Ahmad, A. R. (2014). Moderating effects of work environment on motivation to learn and perceived training transfer: Empirical evidence from a bank. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 8(6), 344-361.
12. Kurniawaty, K., Ramly, M., & Ramlawati, R. (2019). The effect of work environment, stress, and job satisfaction on employee turnover intention. *Management science letters*, 9(6), 877-886.
13. Mobley, W. H. (2011), "Pergantian Karyawan: Sebab, Akibat dan Pengendaliannya. Alih Bahasa: Nurul Imam". PT.
14. Pustaka Binaman Press indo Jakarta. Nejati, M., Rabiei, S., & Jabbour, C. J. C. (2017). Envisioning the invisible: Understanding the synergy between green human resource management and green supply chain management in manufacturing firms in Iran in light of the moderating effect of employees' resistance to change. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 168, 163-172.
15. Sinniah, S., & Kamil, N. M. (2017). The influence of human resource practices on turnover intention: The case of a telecommunication company in Malaysia. *Malaysian Management Review*, 52(1), 45–61.
16. Siyambalapitiya, J., Zhang, X., & Liu, X. (2018). Green human resource management: A proposed model in the context of Sri Lanka's tourism industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 201, 542-555.
17. Wan, Q., Li, Z., Zhou, W., & Shang, S. (2018). Effects of work environment and job characteristics on the turnover intention of experienced nurses: The mediating role of work engagement. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 74(6), 1332-1341.
18. Zeytinoglu, I. U., Denton, M., Davies, S., Baumann, A., Blythe, J., & Boos, L. (2007). Deteriorated external work environment, heavy workload and nurses' job satisfaction and turnover intention. *Canadian Public Policy*, 33(Supplement 1), S31-S47.